

Bioregional Photographic Guide and Identification Key to the Seagrass Species of the World and their Flowering Parts

Global seagrass distribution shown as blue points and polygons and geographic bioregions: 1. Temperate North Atlantic, 2. Tropical Atlantic, 3. Mediterranean, 4. Temperate North Pacific, 5. Tropical Indo-Pacific, 6. Temperate Southern Oceans (Short et al. 2007 JEMBE 350: 3-20).

Seagrass Bioregional Species Key:

1 Temperate North Atlantic Bioregion

Species identification key including photo guide, global range maps, drawings, and flowers.

From:
SeagrassNet
Fred Short
University of New Hampshire
603-659-3313 cell
fredtshort@gmail.com
www.SeagrassNet.org

With ratings from:
IUCN Red List of Threatened Species
Seagrass Red List

*Bioregional Guide to the Seagrass Species of the World. 2025. F.T. Short.
Available on-line www.SeagrassNet.org.*

Zm *Zostera marina*

Bioregion
1

Key

- Flat leaves to 3 m with closed sheath
- Leaf tip smoothly rounded
- Rhizome robust with terminal shoots
- 2 bundles of roots per node
- Monoecious

Flowering Parts

female & male

female

seedling

seed

Extinction Risk: Least Concern

Hw *Halodule wrightii*

Extinction Risk: Least Concern

Key

- Leaves flat and thin
- Leaf tip usually 2 points
- Leaves 2-22 cm long
- Rhizome whitish
- Dioecious
- Depth -1 to 20 m
- Sometimes leaves red or black

Flowering Parts

Rm *Ruppia maritima*

Key

- Leaves flat and thin
- Leaf tapers to tip to point
- Leaves 4-22 cm long
- Depth -1 to 20 m

Flowering Parts

Extinction Risk: Least Concern

Rc *Ruppia cirrhosa*

Extinction Risk: Least Concern

Bioregion

1

Key

- Leaves flat and thin
- Leaf tapers to tip, 25 cm long
- Fruits cluster on spiral stem
- Depth intertidal to 20 m

Flowering Parts

Zn *Nanozostera noltii*

Bioregion
1

Extinction Risk: Least Concern

Found in the
Eastern Atlantic

Key

- Flat narrow leaves to 30 cm with open sheath
- Leaf tip rounded and unevenly notched
- Thin rhizome, shoots at each node
- Flowers on branched stem
- Monoecious

Flowering Parts

Stage

Description

- | | |
|-----|---|
| I | Yellow-green spathe, sheath closed; pistils and stamens are visible, aligned onto the stem |
| II | Pistils (IIa) and/or stamens erected (IIb); styles and stigma and/or anthers are outside the sheath |
| III | Stigma brown, start to depart from spathe; often with stamens already detached from the spathe |
| IV | Green spathe with immature seeds; sheath closed |
| V | Green/brown spathe, dark brown seeds are visible, sheath open |

Ankel et al 2021

Cn *Cymodocea nodosa*

Bioregion
1

Key

- Flat leaves to 30 cm
- Leaf tip rounded, slightly serrated
- Rhizome robust with one root per node
- Flowers emerge from sheath
- Dioecious

Flowering
Parts

fruit

male

Extinction Risk: Least Concern

Found in the
Eastern Atlantic

Seagrass Bioregional Species Key:

2

Tropical Atlantic Bioregion

Species identification key including photo guide, global range maps, drawings, and flowers.

From:

SeagrassNet

Fred Short
University of New Hampshire
603-659-3313 cell
fredtshort@gmail.com
www.SeagrassNet.org

With ratings from:

IUCN Red List of Threatened Species

Seagrass Red List

*Bioregional Guide to the Seagrass Species of the World. 2025. F.T. Short.
Available on-line www.SeagrassNet.org.*

Tt *Thalassia testudinum*

- Key
- Flat leaves with small dark tannin cells
 - Fibrous leaf sheath
 - Rhizome with scale between nodes
 - Leaves 10-60 cm long
 - Dioecious
 - Often with red leaves

Extinction Risk: Least Concern

Flowering Parts

male buds

male female

young fruit

Sf *Syringodium filiforme*

- Key
- Leaves cylindrical
 - Leaf tips taper
 - Leaves 10-60 cm long
 - Dioecious

Flowering Parts

Extinction Risk: Least Concern

Male

female

fruits

Hw *Halodule wrightii*

Key

- Leaves flat and thin
- Leaf tip usually 2 points
- Leaves 2-22 cm long
- Rhizome whitish
- Dioecious
- Depth -1 to 20 m
- Sometimes leaves red or black

Flowering Parts

Extinction Risk: Least Concern

Hv *Halodule beaudettei*

- Key
- Leaves flat and thin
 - Leaf tip with 3 points, long central tooth
 - Leaves 15 cm long
 - Dioecious
 - Depth 0 to 10 m

Extinction Risk: Data Deficient

Hd *Halophila decipiens*

Key

- Paddle-shaped leaves
- Leaf hairs on both sides
- Leaf margins serrated
- Leaves 1-4 cm long
- Monoecious
- Depth 0 to 30 m

Flowering Parts

male & female

fruit

Extinction Risk: Least Concern

HI *Halophila baillonii*

Key

- Leaves in rosette on 1-6 cm stem
- 4-5 leaves per rosette
- Leaf margins serrated
- Leaves 2-3 cm long, rounded tip
- Dioecious

Extinction Risk: **Vulnerable**

Flowering Parts

He *Halophila engelmanni*

- Key
- Leaves in rosette on stem
 - 5-8 leaves per rosette
 - Pointed leaves with small petiole
 - Leaves 2-5 cm long
 - Dioecious
 - Depth 0 to 5 m

Extinction Risk: **Near Threatened**

Flowering Parts

Ho *Halophila ovalis*

Previously *Halophila johnsonii* in Florida, USA

Shutterstock

Key

- Oval-shaped leaves, 1-4 cm long
- Leaves often red or purple
- No leaf hairs
- Leaf margins smooth
- Depth 0 to 10 m
- Dioecious

Flowering Parts

female

male

Extinction Risk: Least Concern

Hs *Halophila stipulacea*

Invasive species

- Elongated paddle-shaped leaves to 6cm
- Leaf stippled and bullate, tip serrated
- Distinctive scales cover the stem
- Depth 0 to 60m
- Dioecious
- Range expanding

Extinction Risk: Least Concern

Flowering Parts

male

female

G Koplovitz

Rm *Ruppia maritima*

Bioregion
2

Key

- Leaves flat and thin
- Leaf tapers to tip
- Leaves 4-22 cm long
- Depth -1 to 20 m

Extinction Risk: Least Concern

male

Flowering Parts

female

fruit

Seagrass Bioregional Species Key:

3 Mediterranean Bioregion

Species identification key including photo guide, global range maps, drawings, and flowers.

From:

SeagrassNet

Fred Short
University of New Hampshire
603-659-3313 cell
fredtshort@gmail.com
www.SeagrassNet.org

With ratings from:

IUCN Red List of Threatened Species

[Seagrass Red List](#)

*Bioregional Guide to the Seagrass Species of the World. 2025. F.T. Short.
Available on-line www.SeagrassNet.org.*

Po *Posidonia oceanica*

Bioregion
3

- Key
- Leaves 40-50 cm
 - Leaf tip rounded
 - Rhizome robust, brush-like and fibrous
 - Flowers emerge on a stem
 - Monoecious

Flowering
Parts

Extinction Risk: Least Concern

Zm *Zostera marina*

Bioregion
3

Key

- Flat leaves to 3 m with closed sheath
- Leaf tip smoothly rounded
- Rhizome robust with terminal shoots
- 2 bundles of roots per node
- Monoecious

Flowering Parts

female
& male

Seedling

Extinction Risk: Least Concern

Zn *Nanozostera noltii*

Bioregion
3

- Key**
- Flat narrow leaves to 30 cm with open sheath
 - Leaf tip rounded and unevenly notched
 - Thin rhizome, shoots at each node
 - Flowers on branched stem
 - Monoecious

Extinction Risk: Least Concern

Flowering Parts

Ankel et al 2021

Stage	Description
I	Yellow-green spathe, sheath closed; pistils and stamens are visible, aligned onto the stem
II	Pistils (IIa) and/or stamens erected (IIb); styles and stigma and/or anthers are outside the sheath
III	Stigma brown, start to depart from spathe; often with stamens already detached from the spathe
IV	Green spathe with immature seeds; sheath closed
V	Green/brown spathe, dark brown seeds are visible, sheath open

Cn *Cymodocea nodosa*

Bioregion
3

- Key
- Flat leaves to 30 cm
 - Leaf tip rounded, slightly serrated
 - Rhizome robust with one root per node
 - Flowers emerge from sheath
 - Dioecious

Flowering
Parts

fruit

Extinction Risk: Least Concern

male

Hd *Halophila decipiens*

Bioregion
3

- Key
- Paddle-shaped leaves
 - Leaf hairs on both sides
 - Leaf margins serrated
 - Leaves 1-4 cm long
 - Monoecious
 - Depth 0-30 m

Extinction Risk: Least Concern

male & female

fruit

Hs *Halophila stipulacea*

Invasive species

Bioregion
3

Key

- Elongated paddle-shaped leaves to 6cm
- Leaf stippled and bullate, tip serrated
- Distinctive scales cover the stem
- Depth 0 to 60m
- Dioecious
- Range expanding

Extinction Risk: Least Concern

Flowering Parts

male

female

G Kopllovitz

Rc *Ruppia cirrhosa*

Extinction Risk: Least Concern

Key

- Leaves flat and thin
- Leaf tapers to tip, 25 cm long
- Fruits cluster on spiral stem
- Depth intertidal to 20 m

Flowering Parts

Rm *Ruppia maritima*

Bioregion
3

Key

- Leaves flat and thin
- Leaf tapers to tip
- Leaves 4-22 cm long
- Depth -1 to 20 m

Extinction Risk: Least Concern

male

Flowering Parts

female

fruit

Hw *Halodule wrightii*

Extinction Risk: Least Concern

Key

- Leaves flat and thin
- Leaf tip with 2-3 points
- Leaves 2-22 cm long
- Rhizome whitish
- Dioecious
- Depth -1 to 20 m
- Sometimes leaves red or black

Flowering Parts

Seagrass Bioregional Species Key:

4 Temperate North Pacific Bioregion

Species identification key including photo guide, global range maps, drawings, and flowers.

From:

SeagrassNet

Fred Short
University of New Hampshire
603-659-3313 cell
fredshort@gmail.com
www.SeagrassNet.org

With ratings from:

IUCN Red List of Threatened Species

Seagrass Red List

*Bioregional Guide to the Seagrass Species of the World. 2025. F.T. Short.
Available on-line www.SeagrassNet.org.*

Zm *Zostera marina*

Bioregion
4

- Key
- Flat leaves to 3 m with closed sheath
 - Leaf tip smoothly rounded
 - Rhizome robust with terminal shoots
 - 2 bundles of roots per node
 - Monoecious

Flowering Parts

Seedling

Seed

Extinction Risk: Least Concern

Zj *Nanozostera japonica*

Bioregion
4

- Key
- Notched rounded leaf tip
 - Narrow leaf blades (2-5 mm)
 - Leaves 7-30 cm long
 - Monoecious
 - Intertidal - shallow subtidal

Flowering Parts

Extinction Risk: Least Concern

Pr *Phyllospadix serrulatus*

Bioregion
4

Attached to rocks

Key

- Flat leaves to 130 cm
- Rounded/flattened tip
- Serrated leaf edges
- 5-7 leaf veins
- Dioecious

Extinction Risk: Least Concern

Ps *Phyllospadix scouleri*

Bioregion
4

Attached to rocks

- Key
- Leaves, bi-convex cross-section, to 200cm
 - Rounded/flattened/notched tip
 - Rhizome internodes with yellow/gray fibers
 - 3 leaf veins
 - Dioecious

Extinction Risk: Least Concern

Pt *Phyllospadix torreyi*

Bioregion

4

Attached to rocks

Key

- Rolled leaves to 200cm
- Rounded slightly notched tip
- 3 leaf veins
- Dioecious

Extinction Risk: Least Concern

Za *Zostera asiatica*

Bioregion
4

- Key
- Flat leaves to 150 cm
 - Flattened notched tip
 - Thick rhizome
 - Seeds 3-5mm brown and smooth
 - Monoecious

Extinction Risk: Near Threatened

Zs *Zostera caespitosa*

Bioregion
4

Key

- Flat leaves to 70 cm with rounded notched tip
- Flowering shoot to 60 cm with many branches
- Rhizome robust with short internodes
- Persistent sheath giving a tufted appearance
- Monoecious

Extinction Risk: **Vulnerable**

Z1 *Zostera caulescens*

Bioregion
4

Key

- Flat leaves 10-100cm with a short sharp tip
- Flowering shoot to 7m with many branches
- Leaf tip smoothly rounded with central point
- Rhizome robust with terminal shoots
- Monoecious

Extinction Risk: Near Threatened

Zf *Zostera pacifica*

Bioregion
4

Key

- Flat leaves to 3 m with closed sheath
- Leaf tip smoothly rounded
- Rhizome robust with terminal shoots
- 2 bundles of roots per node
- Monoecious
- Confused with Za and Zm in N America

Extinction Risk: **Vulnerable**

Pi *Phyllospadix iwatensis*

Attached to rocks

Bioregion
4

Key

- Flat leaves to 150cm with rounded tip
- Yellowish/brown rhizome
- 5 leaf veins
- Dioecious

www.inaturalist.org/taxa

Extinction Risk: **Vulnerable**

Pj *Phyllospadix japonicus*

Bioregion
4

Attached to rocks

Key

- Flat leaves to 100cm with rounded tip
- Black rhizome internode fibers
- 3 leaf veins
- Dioecious

Extinction Risk: **Endangered**

Roofs in Chinese village

Hw *Halodule wrightii*

Bioregion
4

- Key
- Leaves flat and thin
 - Leaf tip usually 2 points
 - Leaves 2-22 cm long
 - Rhizome whitish
 - Dioecious
 - Depth -1 to 20 m
 - Sometimes leaves appear red or black

Extinction Risk: Least Concern

Flowering Parts

fruit

female

Rm *Ruppia maritima*

Bioregion
4

Key

- Leaves flat and thin
- Leaf tapers to tip
- Leaves 4-22 cm long
- Depth -1 to 20 m

Extinction Risk: Least Concern

male

Flowering Parts

female

fruit

Hd *Halophila decipiens*

Bioregion
4

Key

- Paddle-shaped leaf
- Leaf hairs on both side
- Leaf margins serrated
- Leaves 1-4 cm long
- Monoecious
- Depth 0-30 m

Flowering Parts

male & female

fruit

Extinction Risk: Least Concern

HK *Halophila nipponica*

Bioregion
4

- Key**
- Paddle-shaped leaves, no hairs
 - Leaf margins smooth
 - Leaves 1-5cm long
 - Depth 0-30 m

Fig. 2. Morphology of *Halophila nipponica* off the southern coast of Korea. (A) Male flower (arrow) with three purple stamens. (B) Female flower with ovoid ovary and three styles. (C) Leaf blade with 12 pairs of cross-veins. (D) An ovoid fruit. (E) Seed. (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of the article.)

Extinction Risk: Data Deficient

From Jeong Bae Kim et al 2009

Seagrass Bioregional Species Key:

5 Tropical Indo-Pacific Bioregion

Species identification key including photo guide, global range maps, drawings, and flowers.

From:

SeagrassNet

Fred Short
University of New Hampshire
603-659-3313 cell
fredtshort@gmail.com
www.SeagrassNet.org

With ratings from:

IUCN Red List of Threatened Species

Seagrass Red List

*Bioregional Guide to the Seagrass Species of the World. 2025. F.T. Short.
Available on-line www.SeagrassNet.org.*

Th *Thalassia hemprichii*

Bioregion
5

Key

- Rounded serrated leaf tip
- Leaves 10-40 cm, often sickle-shaped
- Rhizome with scale leaves between shoots
- Dioecious
- Sometimes dark tannin spots on leaves
- Sometimes with red leaves in shallows

Extinction Risk: Least Concern

Flowering Parts

fruit

male

Si *Syringodium isoetifolium*

Bioregion
5

Key

- Leaves cylindrical
- Leaf tips taper
- Leaves 7-30 cm long
- Dioecious

Extinction Risk: Least Concern

Flowering Parts

male

female

fruit

Hp *Halodule pinifolia*

- Key
- Rounded leaf tips with marginal points
 - One central leaf vein
 - Pale rhizome with clean black leaf scars
 - Leaves 10 – 30 cm long
 - Depth intertidal to 20 m
 - Dioecious

Extinction Risk: Least Concern

Flowering Parts

Hu *Halodule uninervis*

Bioregion
5

Key

- Leaves flat
- Leaf tip with 3 points
- Rhizome whitish with black leaf scars
- Leaves 10 – 30 cm long
- Depth intertidal to 20 m
- Dioecious

Flowering Parts

Extinction Risk: Least Concern

Hw *Halodule wrightii*

Key

- Leaves flat and thin
- Leaf tip usually 2 points
- Leaves 2-22 cm long
- Rhizome whitish
- Dioecious
- Depth -1 to 20 m
- Sometimes leaves red or black

Flowering Parts

Extinction Risk: Least Concern

Cr *Cymodocea rotundata*

Key

- Smooth rounded-to-squared leaf tip
- Leaf scar fully encircles vertical stem
- Narrow leaf blades (2-5 mm)
- Leaves 7-20 cm long with 9-15 veins
- Dioecious
- Often with red leaves

Flowering Parts

male

female

fruit

Extinction Risk: Least Concern

Cs *Cymodocea serrulata*

- Key
- Serrated rounded leaf tip
 - Leaf scar not encircling vertical stem
 - Wide leaf blades (4-12 mm)
 - Leaves 6-15 cm with 13-17 veins
 - Triangle shaped sheath
 - Dioecious
 - Often with red cross-stripes on leaves

Flowering Parts

male

female

Seed

Extinction Risk: Least Concern

Tc *Thalassodendron ciliatum*

Bioregion
5

- Key
- Cluster of leaves on an erect stem
 - Leaves 10-20 cm
 - Sickle-shaped leaves with serrated tips
 - Rhizome woody
 - Dioecious
 - Leaves often have red cross-stripes

Extinction Risk: Least Concern

Flowering Parts

Ea *Enhalus acoroides*

Key

- Smooth rounded leaf tip
- Leaves 30 cm - 2m long
- Leaf edge rolls around tough fiber
- Wide leaf blades (10-20 mm)
- Rhizome with long black bristles
- Depth intertidal to 2 m
- Dioecious

Flowering Parts

seed release

Extinction Risk: Least Concern

Hd *Halophila decipiens*

Key

- Paddle-shaped leaves
- Leaf hairs on both sides
- Leaf margins serrated
- Leaves 1-4 cm long
- Monoecious
- Depth 0-30 m

Extinction Risk: Least Concern

Flowering Parts

male & female

fruit

Ho *Halophila ovalis*

Bioregion
5

Shutterstock

Key

- Oval-shaped leaves
- Leaves 1-4 cm long
- No leaf hairs
- Leaf margins smooth
- Depth 0-10 m
- Dioecious

Flowering Parts

female

male

Extinction Risk: Least Concern

Hm *Halophila minor*

- Key
- Small oval leaves
 - 4 - 8 cross veins
 - Leaves 8 to 13 mm long
 - No hairs on leaf surface
 - Often intertidal
 - Dioecious

Extinction Risk: Least Concern

Flowering Parts

Ho *Halophila hawaiiiana*

Extinction Risk: **Vulnerable**

Key

- Leaves 1-4 cm long
- No leaf hairs
- Leaf margins smooth
- Dioecious
- Depth 0 -10 m

Flowering Parts

Hn *Halophila spinulosa*

Bioregion
5

Key

- Many oval-shaped leaves on a single stem
- Leaf edges finely serrated
- Wiry rhizome with stems to 30 cm
- Depth 0 -10 m
- Male and female different stems same plant

Extinction Risk: Least Concern

Flowering Parts

female

male

Hb *Halophila beccarii*

Bioregion
5

Key

- 5+ elongated oval leaves in clusters
- Leaves 0.5 –2 mm wide
- Leaves up to 13 mm long
- Often intertidal
- Dioecious

Extinction Risk: **Vulnerable**

Flowering Parts

female

male

seed

Ht

Halophila tricostata

Bioregion
5

Halophila tricostata

Key

- Clusters of 3 leaves on vertical stem
- Leaf with mid-vein and no cross veins
- Leaf margins finely serrated
- Dioecious
- Depth 0-30 m

Extinction Risk: Least Concern

Hs *Halophila stipulacea*

Bioregion
5

- Elongated paddle-shaped leaves to 6cm
- Leaf stippled and bullate, tip serrated
- Distinctive scales cover the stem
- Depth 0-60m
- Dioecious
- Range expanding

Extinction Risk: Least Concern

Flowering Parts

male

G Koplovitz

female

Zj *Nanozostera japonica*

Key

- Smooth rounded leaf tip
- Narrow leaf blades (2-5 mm)
- Leaves 7-20 cm long
- Monoecious
- Depth intertidal - shallow subtidal

Flowering Parts

Extinction Risk: Least Concern

Zc *Nanozostera muelleri*

Shaun Lee 2024

Tony Strazzari

Extinction Risk: Least Concern

Key

- Round leaf tip deeply notched
- Strap-like leaf blades (1-3 mm wide)
- Leaves 10-60 cm long
- Persistent leaf sheath
- Monoecious
- Previously known as *Zostera capricorni*

Flowering Parts

Rachel Hooks 2024

de Kock et al. 2016

female

Zp *Nanozostera capensis*

Key

- Round indented leaf tip
- Leaf with staggered cross veins
- Strap-like leaf blades (0.5-2.5 mm)
- Leaves 10-115 cm long
- Persistent leaf sheath
- Monoecious

Extinction Risk: Least Concern

Flowering Parts

fruit

Rm *Ruppia maritima*

Key

- Leaves flat and thin
- Leaf tapers to tip
- Leaves 4-22 cm long
- Depth -1 to 20 m

Extinction Risk: Least Concern

male

Flowering Parts

female

fruit

Seagrass Bioregional Species Key:

6 Temperate Southern Oceans Bioregion

Species identification key including photo guide, global range maps, drawings, and flowers.

From:

SeagrassNet

Fred Short
University of New Hampshire
603-659-3313 cell
fredtshort@gmail.com
www.SeagrassNet.org

With ratings from:

IUCN Red List of Threatened Species

Seagrass Red List

*Bioregional Guide to the Seagrass Species of the World. 2025. F.T. Short.
Available on-line www.SeagrassNet.org.*

Pa

Posidonia australis

Bioregion

6

Key

- Leaves 40-60 cm
- Leaf tip rounded
- Rhizome robust, brush-like and fibrous
- Flowers emerge on a stem
- Monoecious

Flowering Parts

Photos from Gary Kendrick

Extinction Risk: Least Concern

Pn *Posidonia sinuosa*

Bioregion
6

Justin McDonald

Key

- Leaves ribbon like, 140 cm
- Leaf tip rounded
- Leaf sheath membranous
- Flowers emerge at base
- Monoecious

Extinction Risk: Least Concern

Pg

Posidonia angustifolia

Bioregion

6

Gary Kendrick

Key

- Leaves ribbon like, 80 cm
- Leaf tip rounded
- Rhizome robust, pale fibers
- Flowers emerge on a stem
- Monoecious

Extinction Risk: Least Concern

Pf

Posidonia ostenfeldii

Bioregion

6

Key

- Leaves thick, round and up to 180 cm
- Leaf tip rounded
- Rhizome enclosed in fine pale fibers
- Flowers emerge on a stem
- Monoecious

Extinction Risk: Least Concern

Gary Kendrick

Pd *Posidonia denhartogii*

Bioregion
6

Key

- Leaves biconvex 120 cm
- Leaf tip rounded
- Rhizome robust, pale fibers
- Flowers emerge on a stem
- Monoecious

Extinction Risk: Least Concern

Aa *Amphibolis antarctica*

Bioregion
6

GK

Key

- Wiry stems 1.5 m long
- Leaf crowns of 6-10 bidentate blades
- Strap-like leaf blades (5 cm) twisted

Extinction Risk: Least Concern

seedling

Ag *Amphibolis griffithii*

Bioregion
6

- Key
- Wiry stems 1.0 m long
 - Leaf crowns of 4-5 notched blades
 - Strap-like leaf blades (3-10 cm)

Extinction Risk: Least Concern

ian.umces.edu

Zo *Heterozostera polychlamys*

Bioregion
6

Key

- Squared leaf tip, shallow notch
- Wiry erect stems, not black
- Strap-like leaf blades (0.5-2.5 mm wide)
- Shoot 100 cm long

Lotte Horn

Extinction Risk: Least Concern

Australia only

Z† *Heterozostera tasmanica*

Bioregion
6

- Key**
- Rounded leaf tip, deeply notched
 - Wiry erect stems, not black
 - Strap-like leaf blades (35cm long)

Extinction Risk: Data Deficient

Australia only

Zr *Heterozostera nigricaulis*

Bioregion

6

Key

- Squared leaf tip, notched
- Wiry erect stems, black
- Shoot 100 cm long

Extinction Risk: Least Concern

Zh *Heterozostera chilensis*

Bioregion

6

Key

- Squared leaf tip, notched
- Wiry erect stems, dark
- Strap-like leaf blades (0.5-2.5 mm wide)
- Shoot 100 cm long

Extinction Risk: **Endangered**

Chile only

Rm *Ruppia maritima*

Bioregion
6

- Key
- Leaves flat and thin
 - Leaf tapers to tip
 - Leaves 4-22 cm long
 - Depth -1-20 m

Extinction Risk: Least Concern

male

Flowering Parts

female

fruit

Si *Syringodium isoetifolium*

Bioregion

6

Key

- Leaves cylindrical
- Leaf tips taper
- Leaves 7-30 cm long
- Dioecious

Extinction Risk: Least Concern

Flowering Parts

male

female

fruit

Tc *Thalassodendron ciliatum*

Bioregion
6

- Key
- Cluster of leaves on an erect stem
 - Leaves 10-40 cm
 - Sickle-shaped leaves with serrated tips
 - Rhizome woody
 - Dioecious
 - Leaves often have red cross-stripes

Extinction Risk: Least Concern

Flowering Parts

Tp *Thalassodendron pachyrhizum*

Bioregion
6

- Key
- Cluster of leaves on an erect stem
 - Leaves 10-15 cm, thin ribbons
 - Sickle-shaped leaves with serrated tips
 - Rhizome woody
 - Dioecious

Extinction Risk: Least Concern

Australia only

Zc *Nanozostera muelleri*

Bioregion
6

Shaun Lee 2024

Tony Strazzari

Key

- Round leaf tip deeply notched
- Strap-like leaf blades (1-2 mm)
- Leaves 10-60 cm long
- Persistent leaf sheath
- Monoecious
- Previously known as *Zostera capricorni*

Extinction Risk: Least Concern

Flowering Parts

Rachel Hooks 2024

de Kock et al. 2016

female

Zp *Nanozostera capensis*

Bioregion
6

- Key
- Round indented leaf tip
 - Leaf with staggered cross veins
 - Strap-like leaf blades (0.5-2.5 mm)
 - Leaves 10-115 cm long
 - Persistent leaf sheath
 - Monoecious

Extinction Risk: Least Concern

Flowering Parts

Ha *Halophila australis*

Bioregion
6

Key

- Oval-shaped leaf pairs
- Leaves 2-7 cm long
- No leaf hairs
- Leaf margins smooth
- Dioecious
- Depth 0-10 m

Flowering Parts

Flowers unique on an erect stalk, female with 6 styles.

Extinction Risk: Least Concern

Ho *Halophila ovalis*

Bioregion

6

Shutterstock

Key

- Oval-shaped leaves
- Leaves 1-4 cm long
- No leaf hairs
- Leaf margins smooth
- Depth 0-10 m
- Dioecious

Flowering Parts

female

male

Extinction Risk: Least Concern

Hd *Halophila decipiens*

Bioregion

6

Key

- Paddle-shaped leaves
- Leaf hairs on both sides
- Leaf margins serrated
- Leaves 1-4 cm long
- Monoecious
- Depth 0-30 m

Extinction Risk: Least Concern

Flowering Parts

male & female

fruit

Global Seagrass Species References

den Hartog, C., 1970. **The Sea-Grasses of the World**. North-Holland Publication Co., Amsterdam.

Short, F.T. and R.G. Coles (eds.). 2001. **Global Seagrass Research Methods**. Elsevier Science B.V., Amsterdam. 473 pp.

Green, E.P. and Short, F.T. (eds.). 2003. **World Atlas of Seagrasses**. University of California Press, Berkeley, USA. 324 pp.

Short, F.T., Carruthers, T.J.B., Dennison, W.C., Waycott, M. 2007. **Global seagrass distribution and diversity: a bioregional model**. *Journal of Experimental Marine Biology and Ecology* 350: 3–20.

Short FT, Polidoro B, Livingstone SR, Carpenter KE, Bandeira S, Bujang JS, Calumpong HP, Carruthers TJB, Coles RG, Dennison WC, Erftemeijer PLA, Fortes MD, Freeman AS, Jagtap TG, Kamal AHM, Kendrick GA, Kenworthy WJ, La Nafie YA, Nasution IM, Orth RJ, Prathep A, Sanciangco JC, van Tussenbroek B, Vergara SG, Waycott M, Zieman, JC. 2011. **Extinction risk assessment of the world's seagrass species**. *Biol Conserv.* 44: 1961–71.

Bioregion 2 Guide

van Tussenbroek, B. I., M-G. Barba-Santos, J. G., R., Wong, K. Van Dijk, M. Waycott. 2010. **A Guide to the tropical seagrasses of the Western Atlantic**, Universidad Nacional Autónoma de México, October 2010. ISBN: 978-607-02-1222-2

Bioregion 5 Guides

El Shaffai, A. 2016. **Field Guide to Seagrasses of the Red Sea**. Roupheal, A. and Abdulla, A. Second edition. Gland, Switzerland: IUCN and Courbevoie, France: Total Foundation. viii + 56 pp.

Waycott, M., K. McMahon, J. Mellors, A. Calladine and D. Kleine. 2004. **A Guide to Tropical Seagrasses of the Indo-West Pacific**. James Cook University, Townsville. 72 pp.

Bioregion 6 Guide

Waycott, M, K. McMahon, P. Lavery. 2014. **A Guide to Southern Temperate Seagrasses**. CSIRO Publication – April 28, 2014. 109 p.

Bioregional Guide to the Seagrass Species of the World. 2025. F.T. Short.